

Professional and Personal Qualities of Public Secondary Teachers in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2015 – 2016 in terms of teachers' profile, extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities including their strengths and weaknesses. The respondent of the study covered nineteen (19) public secondary schools with a total enumeration of 305 teachers and 19 school administrators. The salient findings of the study are as follows: Most of the teachers were females, within the age bracket from 21-39 years, BS graduates, have attended seminars/trainings with five (5) attendance or less for the past three (3) years and have been service for 10 years or less; The extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities were described as "Often"; There were no significant differences on the extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities across profile variables age, gender, years of teaching experience and seminars/trainings attended except highest educational attainment; There was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice professional qualities; There was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities; There were strengths and weaknesses of teachers in the practice of professional and personal qualities. In some areas, there were more strengths than weaknesses and the proposed action plan to improve the extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities was formulated.

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn. Most of the teachers were not fully equipped with the needed trainings and experiences in the different areas of professional and personal qualities; Teachers had not reached the desired extent of teachers' practices especially along personal qualities; Highest educational attainment has more effect than profile variables age, gender, years of teaching experience and seminars/training attended; The perception of teachers on the extent to which they manifest professional qualities was reinforced by the perception of their school administrators. Hence, their perceptions do not vary; The perceptions of teachers and their school administrators were of the same level; The strengths of teachers dominate their weaknesses and the action plan to improve the professional and personal qualities of teachers was formulated.

Keywords: *professional qualities, personal qualities, public secondary teachers, teacher profile, teaching competencies, educational management, Calasiao Pangasinan, teacher development, instructional competence, personal attributes*

Chapter 1

The Problem Rationale

Teaching has always been thought of as one of the noblest of professions; and a teacher, likewise, building character and personality of a learner depends on the prowess of a good teacher and the capability to create a meaningful landmark to inculcate to the mind and spirit the significance of knowledge and understanding with the world. (Zhu, 2019).

The school is very much alive when the teachers are dynamic, alert and zealous of their teaching, research and service functions. In order to articulate the philosophy, vision and mission of the school in relation to the changing needs of the immediate community that it serves and the society, in general, of which it is an integral part, the teacher has a tremendous task. The teacher is not just a cog in the wheel, is the wheel in the total complex of the educational system is the central figure in the school system, notwithstanding the pupils/students, translate into commodity and transform values and attitudes into functional attributes.

In line with his noble commitment to facilitate learning and to help pursue thrusts and programs, teachers are expected to uphold the professional standard of the teaching profession by manifesting a genuine enthusiasm and pride in their calling.

Since teaching is a multifaceted human activity for it involves a wide range of planning, teaching strategies, interactions, organizational arrangement and material resources that take place in the teaching-learning process, teachers are often viewed as the most important variable in the learner's educational environment. There are various factors of teaching that are considered in this complex human endeavor, the teacher's role, the teaching strategies and techniques, the goals and objectives as basis for teaching, the means to attain the desired objectives and the psychological foundations. Inferentially, whatever perspective of teaching people may have there is a common thread of agreement that its ultimate purpose is to direct and facilitate learning. To be more effective, teachers must possess professional and personal qualities.

Professional qualities refer to qualities which can influence teaching-learning process and highly attributive to teaching competence relative to mastery of the subject matter, medium of instruction, methodology of teaching, art of questioning, classroom management and evaluation teaching. Personal qualities refer to the teacher's personality. This includes his philosophy, interests, attitudes, beliefs, emotional maturity and his interrelations with his students, co-teachers, school administrators in the manner he responds to various situations (Timbol, 2018).

The professional and personal qualities undoubtedly influence effectiveness in the moral responsibility they have when they face with students and share their knowledge. It is imperative for them to be constantly aware of the need to utilize every moment with the students to teach them how to think, to open the door to varied experiences in life, to touch their hearts, to inspire them to reach the highest peak of their goal. These are some of the ultimate reasons why the researcher has decided to conduct this study to be able to improve the extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities of the faculty members of Public High Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao Division of Pangasinan I.

On Professional Qualities

According to Zulueta (2006), the professional qualities of an effective teacher / professor, undoubtedly influence the teaching-learning process. He pointed out some professional qualities of teachers that can contribute to improve one's teaching competence and their total well-being. These are:

1. Mastery of the subject matter. This is the first essential requisite of effective learning. The teacher must have a thorough grasp of the subject he teaches.

Since everybody is aware that a person there is an explosion of knowledge in every field, the teacher should keep abreast and keep up with new trends and development in this area.

2. Understanding the learner. The second essential requisite of effective teaching is knowledge of the nature of children. It is important to understand the basic principles of human growth and development. The teacher should be aware of the different levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of the children. It is important to know their interests, backgrounds, and previous experiences which in effect, can be used in motivating the learners. He must also consider the various stages of development- the physical, social and emotional problems they usually face in growing up. It is not enough to know the different characteristics and traits of every child. Equally important is that the teacher must like the learners. A teacher who has genuine concern and sincere love for children can virtually imbue them with love of studying and learning.

3. Understanding the principles and methods of teaching and skills in the use of strategies and techniques for proper implementation. The teacher should be able to promote learning effectively by knowing what to teach (subject matter), how to teach (method) and the skill appropriate for effective teaching.

Instructional methods covers understanding the curriculum, principles of learning, pedagogical approaches, types of learning, outcomes, the psychology of motivation and how to sustain interest, and individual differences which are the basis for selecting, organizing and grouping learning experiences.

4. General understanding of other branches/field of knowledge. Today, teaching demands that a teacher should possess a general knowledge and understanding of other fields or branches of knowledge. He must keep abreast with the explosion of knowledge and be able to show how his subject relates with other areas of knowledge particularly in providing alternative solutions of societal problems.

Learners at present have wide range of interest and abilities. It is not surprising to hear children talk with some degree of understanding about astronauts and their space exploits. A broad understanding of the arts, languages, literature, philosophy, mathematics, physical science and culture is necessary.

5. Understanding and taking pride of teaching as a profession. Foremost, the teacher must understand his task and the corresponding responsibility. The degree of the teacher's success will depend to a great extent on his attitude and positive out-look toward his job. Teaching involves varied interrelations with other individuals, and therefore, he must know how to work effectively with students and other persons involved in the school. These include school administrators, co-teachers, parents, non-teaching administrative personnel and other members of the community. He must value and uphold ethical professional relationships with other people at all times. He must also be aware of the importance of professional organizations for teachers and be an active member. Finally, he must be aware of the need for keeping abreast with the demands, changes

and challenges in education through various in-service education programs.

On the other hand, Calderon (2005) pointed out some of the professional qualities which are good attributes to an exemplary teaching-learning process.

There are as follows:

1. **Mastery of the subject matter.** This refers to the subject the teacher should teach. Naturally, the teacher should teach the subject he knows very well. It is needless to underscore the fact that a teacher must have a complete mastery of the subject he teaches. It is therefore imperative that a teacher must have a complete mastery of the subject he teaches so that he has something to give to his students or pupils. This is why prospective teachers are required to specialize in one or two disciplines especially in the higher levels. They are also required to study the basics of other disciplines because sometimes knowledge in one discipline is needed in teaching other disciplines.

2. **Mastery of the methods, strategies, approaches, techniques and tools of teaching.** This refers to the blueprint, the master plan of the procedure that the teacher follows in teaching. Like the carpenter who cannot produce fine furniture with crude tools and methods, the teacher too cannot produce good finished products with crude methods. The teacher, however, does not need to master all the methods, strategies, approaches and techniques found in the books. He needs to master a few, each suitable to a particular teaching situation, which he can utilize with the utmost dexterity to be able to produce the best results. The best method is the one with which the used produces the best results. The teacher however, must provide varied learning experiences to avoid boredom and monotony and to maximize learning among his students.

3. **Mastery of the medium of instruction.** This enables the teacher to explain very clearly his points to his students so that they understand him. If the medium of instruction is English, the teacher must have a good vocabulary and mastery of the rules of grammar of the language. He must be able to speak well with acceptable pronunciation of words and correct grammar. And so with Filipino. It is unthinkable for a teacher to stand before his class only to speak ungrammatical English or Filipino. Worse, he cannot explain the lesson well if he has a very limited vocabulary. The use of mixed English and Filipino where English is the medium of instruction should be avoided. The true essence of bilingualism should be followed, this is, if English is the medium of instruction, English must be used in teaching, if Filipino is the medium of instruction, Filipino should be used in teaching the lesson.

4. **Mastery of lesson planning and organizing instructional materials and other resources.** As in other endeavors, planning is very important to the teacher, particularly lesson planning and planning classroom activities. Good planning ensures that the most important part of the lesson is taken up, makes possible the smooth and logical flow of learning activities, avoids waste but saves time. Planning enable the teacher to accomplish the work he set for himself to do in the most effective way in the shortest time possible. Hence, the teacher must be a master lesson planner. A good written daily lesson plan is necessary in the elementary and high school levels and a good written syllabus for a term is necessary in the tertiary levels.

The teacher must also have a full knowledge of rich community resources of instructional materials and how to organize such materials for instructional purposes. This is so because the lesson is as good as there are instructional materials. The library, aside from the textbook, is a rich source of instructional materials but are mostly verbal, while the environment abounds in audio-visual aids. The teacher should be alert in determining and locating the kinds of instructional materials that he needs from the library and the community.

5. Mastery of the psychology of learning or educational psychology. The teacher must have a mastery of the principles and techniques that make children learn and faster so that he can apply such principles and techniques in his teaching. He must know the factors that facilitate learning such as learning by doing, motivation, reinforcement, discipline, how to deal with individual differences, development of critical thinking, decision-making, self-direction, self-reliance, and countless others to make his teaching very effective and enjoyable too.

6. Mastery in the formulation of goals and objectives. No one can teach without goals and objectives. These are the teachers' guides in teaching. While the teacher must know his instructional goals and objectives, he must also know the goals and objectives of his institution and those of the nation. This is so because he has to formulate his goals and objectives in accordance with institutional and national goals and objectives. For instance, the instructional objective of the teacher is to make his pupils read, the objective of the nation is to make the population literate.

7. Mastery of classroom management including discipline. The teacher is the manager and director of the learning activities and he should see to it that class sessions are started promptly and conducted smoothly and productively. Learning devices are in their proper places and manipulated properly, lighting and ventilation are attended to seats are properly arranged and discipline it at its best. Discipline is at its best when the pupils or students are busy doing their lessons.

Classroom management should be democratic. The essence of democratic classroom management is participation by the students. They participate in discussions, recitations, solving audio-visual devices, mathematical problems, manipulating questioning the teacher, and many other forms of participation. Class activities are so planned that there is a sequential and logical arrangement of student activities and the teacher achieves his objectives to the maximum degree possible within in the allotted time.

8. Mastery of measurement and evaluation. Measurement and evaluation of students' achievements are important tasks of a teacher. He must know when to see and how to construct norm-referenced tests or criterion referenced tests. He must know how to construct measuring instruments such as essay or objective tests, quizzes, and long examinations to measure the achievement of his students and he should check and return them promptly. He must also know how to see the results of his tests especially in remedial teaching. And last but not the least, in fact this is very important, he must know how to transmute raw scores into quality marks or grades with fairness and impartially.

9. Mastery of the techniques of motivation. Motivation is the arousal of interest of the students. This is an important aspect of teaching because unless the students are interested in the lesson they do not pay attention and they do not learn. Their interest in the lesson should be aroused and sustained so that they will learn. A chapter is devoted to the discussion of the different techniques of motivation.

10. Mastery of the art of questioning. Questioning is a very important tool of teaching. There are at least two types of questions. One type is that which elicits factual information and the second type is that which develops analytical and critical thinking, self-direction, and self-reliance.

11. Mastery of the basics of guidance and counseling. The teacher is always a guidance counselor to a certain extent. Consciously or unconsciously he is always giving counsels to his students. He must always be ready to give a good counsel to a student who is badly in need of

such. And he must be approachable always. He must love his learners and be kind to them as a parent loves and counsels his children. He must have sympathy, friendliness, kindness, helpfulness, and a fair level of tolerance.

On Personal Qualities

According to Macaranas (2015), the following are some important personal qualities that teachers must possess. They are: 1. pleasing personal appearance; 2. good physical health and personal hygiene; 3. emotional stability, sound mental health and self-control; 4. superior intelligence; 5. pleasant modulated voice; 6. sympathy, kindness, helpfulness, patience, diligence; integrity, trustworthiness, honesty, sincerity; 8. flexibility, creativity, resourcefulness; 9. fairness, firmness, impartiality, tolerance, patience; 10. sociability, friendliness, cooperativeness; 11. Refinement in words, tact and courtesy, civility; 12. sense of humor, cheerfulness, enthusiasm; 13. positive outlook, encouraging attitude; and 14. promptness, efficiency.

What then are the personal qualities of an effective teacher? Educators and psychologists agree that personal qualities are so interrelated with professional qualifications or qualities that are quite difficult to isolate them. Since personal qualities are intangible, they are difficult to measure. There have been several studies to identify the personal qualities of an effective teacher from student's opinions because it is generally believed that they are the best respondents or subjects of the research regarding the characteristics and traits of teachers. These personal characteristics and traits are related to the five dimensions of the teacher's personality. These are intellectual, physical, social, emotional and ethical or moral.

Quizmundo (2016), pointed out some significant personal qualities of teachers which are as follows: First, the teacher's personality should be pleasant, alive and attractive. This does not rule out people who are physically plain, or even ugly, because any such have great personal charm. But it does rule out such types as the over-excitable, melancholy, frigid, sarcastic, cynical, frustrated, and over-bearing: I would say too, that it excludes all of dull or purely negative personality. I still stick to what I said in my earlier book; that school children probably suffer more from bores than from brutes'.

Secondly, it is not merely desirable but essential for a teacher to have a genuine capacity for sympathy meaning of that word; a capacity to tune in to the minds and feelings of other people, especially, since most teachers are school teachers, to the minds and feelings of children. Closely related with this is the capacity to be tolerant - not, indeed, of what is wrong, but of the frailty and immaturity of human nature which induce people, and again especially children, to make mistakes.

Thirdly, I hold it essential for a teacher to be both intellectually and morally honest. This does not mean being a plaster saint. It means that he will be aware of his intellectual strengths, and limitations, and will have thought about and decided upon the moral principles by which his life shall be guided. There is no contradiction in my going on to say that a teacher should be a bit of an actor. That is part of the technique of teaching, which demands that every now and then a teacher should be able to put on an act to enliven a lesson, correct a fault, or award praise. Children, especially young children, live in a world that is rather larger than life.

A teacher must remain mentally alert. He will not get into the profession if of low intelligence, but it is all too easy, even for people of above-average intelligence, to stagnate intellectually and that means to deteriorate intellectually. A teacher must be quick to adapt himself to any situation, however improbable and able to improvise, if necessary at less than a

moment's notice. On the other hand, a teacher must be capable of infinite patience. This, I may say, is largely a matter of self-discipline and self-training; we are none of us born like that. He must be pretty resilient; teaching makes great demands on nervous energy. And he should be able to take in his stride the innumerable petty irritations any adult dealing with children has to endure.

According to Calderon (2015), there are certain personal qualities that make one a good teacher. These are as follows:

1. **Intelligence.** A teacher has to be intelligent because he is dealing with verbal materials and individuals with varying levels of intelligence. For a teacher in the lower grades, a teacher with a fair level of intelligence may do provided he has the patience, the stamina and fair level of tolerance. But for a teacher in higher levels especially in the tertiary level, the teacher must possess a higher level of intelligence because he is dealing with more difficult subject matter and with individuals in their stage of higher intellectual development.

2. **Punctuality and enthusiasm.** An effective teacher is always punctual and enthusiastic in his teaching. He goes to his class on time and dismisses it as scheduled. He teaches with diligence, not wasting time. He covers as much subject matter as he can but not teaching with diligence are forms of dishonesty. A teacher must be honest to the core. He fulfills faithfully his appointments with his students.

3. **Good physical and mental health.** Taking all other things equal, an unhealthy teacher cannot do what a healthy teacher can do. An unhealthy teacher, physically or mentally, cannot accomplish what he ought to do. Thus, a teacher must be at the peak of his health physically and mentally so that he can go about his business of teaching unhampered by any ailment. He must have emotional stability and self control so that he can teach without tantrums, crankiness or eccentricity.

4. **Loyalty and commitment.** A teacher must be loyal and committed to his profession and to the institution he serves. A teacher is more cooperative, works harder and does any assignment given to him with gladness and finesse if he loves his profession and the institution he serves.

5. **Respect for the dignity of the individual.** The teacher must respect the dignity of any person he comes in contact with especially his superiors, peers, and students. He gives due respect and cooperation to his superiors, treat his peers the way he wants to be treated by them and recognizes the individual worth of his students. He must not cast aspersions, indignities or insults upon his students when they are not doing well in class but must maintain his professional relationship with them as much as possible.

6. **Fair level of tolerance, firmness and impartiality.** A teacher meets all kinds of problems with pupils and students: inattentiveness, not doing well with their lessons, etc. A teacher must maintain a fair level of tolerance for him to be able to endure the ordeal and the stress. He must remember that he cannot make robots out of the children, which should not be done anyway, but they should be developed into well disciplined, intelligent, law abiding, and productive citizens of the country. The teacher must also be firm and impartial in settling problems among the students themselves.

7. **Adaptability.** A teacher should be adaptable, that is, he can adjust himself to any teaching situation. If he can handle a bright class, he can also handle a dull class. If he can handle a tamed class, he can also handle an unruly class which should of course, be brought under disciplinary control. If he can teach in the urban area, he can also teach in the rural area.

8. **Alertness, resourcefulness, creativity.** A teacher must be alert, resourceful, and creative

in dealing with critical teaching situations. He must be resourceful and creative in locating modern learning materials. If his class is drowsy, he can create a situation to arouse its interest so that it becomes active. He can vary his technique, vary his audio-visual materials, inject a clean sense of humor, or whatever to make his alive and active.

9. Appropriate grooming. A teacher must be in appropriate grooming to maintain the dignity of his profession. The attire should not be too showy nor poorly tailored and poorly washed and ironed. The females should not be revealing parts of their bodies that may attract special attention from the males. Pupils are good imitators and so the teacher must provide a good model for the pupils to emulate. He must have a pleasing personal appearance.

10. Christian outlook, missionary spirit. There is not much money in teaching compared with the more lucrative occupations. But it is very rich in service. That is why the teacher must develop a Christian outlook or missionary spirit to make him happy in his job. The teacher is most happy in rendering selfless service when helpful to his students and pupils, always approachable, kind and friendly.

11. Clean sense of humor. A teacher must have a store of clean humorous tales and anecdotes to awaken his students when they become sleepy and inattentive. So much the better if his humorous tales are relevant to his lesson. Clean humor is often a good means of maintaining the interest, attention, cheerfulness and enthusiasm of students.

12. Good professional and human relations. A teacher must have good human relations with his students. He must be kind to them, smiles at them, jokes with them occasionally, or plays with them. But he must let them understand that he is their teacher, they obey his legitimate orders, and maintain their respect for him. He must avoid receiving too many favors or gifts from them except on appropriate occasions. He must let them understand that they will receive the school marks that they deserve depending upon their achievements and not upon their relationship with him.

13. Good moral and ethical character. One thing that a teacher should always try to keep high is his moral and ethical character. He must keep those social and spiritual values that are acceptable not only in his school but in his community as well. A teacher is usually considered and expected to be a model in character and he must maintain that impression. He should avoid committing acts that would tarnish his reputation because his efficiency as a teacher is adversely affected by a bad reputation. He must be a person of honesty, integrity, fairness, impartially and trustworthiness.

14. Desire to grow professionally. A teacher must grow professionally while in service. Change is constantly taking place and what the teacher had learned in school a few years ago may be obsolete now. Hence, he must attend educational conferences, seminars, and workshop. He must read modern books and journals in education and further his studies by taking graduate studies. It is also good if he can join educational associations.

15. Leadership and followership. If a teacher has bright ideas and can sway people to his side of thinking, he may assume the position of leadership among his peers. If he performs the role of follower, he must be cooperative and must follow legitimate orders from his superiors.

16. Love for children. If a teacher has a genuine love for children he will be happy in his job and he becomes efficient otherwise he becomes unhappy and he becomes inefficient. A teacher should treat his pupils as a good parent treats his children.

17. Observes the Code of Professional Ethics. The teaching profession has a code of ethics which explains the relationships of a teacher to the state, to his superiors, to his peers, to

his students and to the people of the community. A teacher should take hold of this code of ethics so that he will know how to relate himself to the different people who have some involvement in his profession.

Competencies of Teachers

Abuera (2014) noted that the need for an adequate knowledge and orientation on the different teaching strategies and techniques for instructional competencies on the part of the school administrators and teachers cannot be underestimated. They are the basic resources for the teachers in the achievement of maximum educational outcomes. On this score, it is important for the secondary school administrators and secondary school teachers to acquire and develop instructional competencies that will provide them direction and stimulate them to work out innovations in the school process.

Galang (2014) specified that the teaching-learning process should be started only when the teacher and the pupils are mentally and emotionally ready to participate in the process. Teacher's techniques are necessary to set the minds and emotions of the pupils. He further emphasized that if the teaching-learning process remain theoretical, as is generally observed, the quality of education remain low.

Macomber (2014) mentioned that no one can expect to meet all the competencies for teaching to the highest degree, either at the time of graduation or at the end of a lifetime career in teaching. But with each year of experience a teachers' professional competence in teaching and other diversified areas of discipline increases and improves.

Naval and Aquino (2014) disclosed that one supervisory technique that has great potential for the increasing knowledge and for the upgrading the competence of teachers is professional reading. As the term implied, a major activity involved is reading by the teachers in using books, periodicals and other materials which deal with various aspect of the teacher's work.

The main advantage of the directed professional reading is the opportunity which gives teachers grow professionally through the various ideas that they get from the materials that they read. Ideas in curriculum development, instructional procedures, classroom control, psychological principles and the recent trends in education cannot but assist the teacher in her efforts to gain new knowledge and new insights all of which will stand her in good stead as she goes about the work.

Salandan (2005) wrote that specialists and educators have been assuring that teacher alone can provide the most conducive and stimulating clients when learning is envisioned to progress in a self-directed and independent manner. They emphasized that the effectiveness of classroom instruction depends largely upon the preparation and competence of the teacher. The attainment of the goals of education depends to a large extent on how the teacher teaches his lesson.

Aquino (2015) maintained that an excellent teacher is a person who has the personal qualities of agreeableness, consideration for others, sincerity and the like, is professionally interested and competent; manifest scholarship and culture; respects children and is respected by children; and establishes wholesome pupil-teacher relationship.

The superior teacher today recognizes the fact that the school is one of the most important community agencies. It is of and for the community. As a responsible leader in such an organization she cannot escape her responsibility of active participation in community life. Whether the people of the community accept it or not, the teacher should participate in all those

activities of the community which have for their objectives the improvement of social and economic conditions.

The study of Abenojar (2015) revealed the following significant findings:

1. Twelve qualities were considered analyzed in connection with effective classroom teaching. Six qualities were unanimously agreed upon by the sixteen respondents' administrators to be the desirable qualities possessed by teachers. They are as follows: (a) dynamic personality including good physical and mental health, (b) knowledge of subject matter and provision for making the subject interesting to pupils, (c) is patient with pupils, (d) evaluates pupils' work fairly, and (e) strives to grow professionally.

2. Eight qualities were given as desirable for effective relations with co-teachers. These qualities were unanimously accepted by the respondents, such as: (a) cooperates willingly with co-teachers; (b) shows respect for co-teachers; and (c) shows understanding and sympathetic attitudes towards co-teachers.

3. Six qualities desired from effective relations with administrators were listed. Three qualifications were accepted by all the respondents: (a) performs his teaching and other assignments competently and efficiently as expected by his administrators; (b) works harmoniously with his principals and supervisors; and (c) shows courtesy and respect to his principal and supervisor. Least desired among the qualities listed was: accepts constructive criticisms that strengthen the school administration.

4. Five desirable qualities for promoting effective relations with parents were enumerated. Three qualities were agreed upon by the respondents. These are (a) seeks the cooperation of parents in the proper guidance and improvement of their children's work in school; (b) works harmoniously with parents in various school projects; and (c) conducts himself properly to merit the confidence and respect of parents. Last among the desired qualities enumerated was: takes an objective stand of parents' criticism against the school.

5. Six qualities desired for effective relationship with the community were given: (a) demonstrates educational leadership in the community; (b) demonstrates moral leadership in the community; (c) links school activities with community life in order to make the school an effective agency with community leaders and agencies. Ranked lowest among the qualities was: takes an objective stand on criticisms by community leaders against the school.

The study of Santos (2013) yielded the following significant findings:

1. All respondents gave "knowing the feeling of unity as a group" as a factor which helps in understanding the needs of the community". The other factors are: (1) having the feeling of physical and economic security; (2) experiencing and feeling of the need for community achievement.

2. There were forty-three respondents who practiced responsibility in meeting the needs of the community and changing its behavior in certain aspects. Thirty-eight respondents practiced secured community support for the school, twenty-seven respondents used the total resources of the community for educational purposes, while twenty-seven respondents defined and established certain basic problems and issues in school and community.

3. As to the participation of the teachers as community leaders, all the respondents said that they held active membership in various organizations, and also engaged in community service. Twenty-seven respondents directed activities of out-of-school youth, while twenty respondents used community resources for curriculum improvement.

4. The means used by these respondents in developing awareness of the values of

community relations were: (1) stands ready to furnish guidance in developing group leadership if it is needed or sought; (2) panning and organizing with fellow teachers various field trips and excursions in the community according to twenty-seven; (3) serves resource persons by helping the pupils to become aware of the class laboratory experiences which enhance leadership which was revealed by thirty-eight; (4) demonstrate their keen leadership by participating in community affairs and providing opportunities for staff participation.

Favila (2015) revealed the following findings:

1. In relation to the competency of the teachers as director of learning the data indicated that they were very competent along the following areas: (1) directing pupils' learning in an effective way; (2) discovering and correcting pupils' difficulty; (3) measuring the progress of pupils' learning; (4) understanding fully the ability of each pupil; (5) applying the principles of individual differences in teaching; and (6) encouraging potential dropouts to continue their studies. Likewise there were respondents who were found to be competent in giving remedial teaching to slow learners.

2. As to the competency of the teachers as mediator of culture the data revealed that they were found to be very competent: (1) in directing class activities designed specifically to develop interest in the field of subject matter; (2) in planning and directing class activities primarily to develop attitudes and ideals; and (3) in inculcating in the minds of pupils cultural values.

3. As to how competent are the respondents in linking the school and the community, the data revealed that the teachers were found to be very competent along the following areas: (1) helping pupils and the community work together to improve both school and the community; (2) helping the pupils understand the school program; and (3) initiating community beautification projects. The areas which how that the teachers were competent were: (1) assisting the community in planning project where pupils take the lead in community improvement; (2) attending barangay meetings; and (3) organizing field trips where pupils study community project and activities; and organizing community clubs.

4. Regarding the competency of the teachers as members of the staff the data portrayed that they were found to be very competent along the following areas: (1) cooperating with school heads and other teachers; (2) being fair in dealing with colleagues; (3) creating a pleasant working atmosphere among colleagues; (4) helping in carrying out the program of activities; and (5) planning and directing extra-curricular activities. The data further revealed that the teachers were found to be competent in suggesting ways to improve teaching-learning conditions.

5. In relation to the competency of the teachers as members of the teaching profession the data indicated that they were competent in the following areas: (1) assisting pupils in planning and testing new techniques and procedures which affected teaching; (2) following the Code of Ethics of the Profession; (3) active member of teachers' association; (4) participation in the activities related to the profession; and (5) interpreting to the public their concern in major problems of the profession.

6. The study revealed that the teachers were found to be very competent teachers. The data further revealed that the teachers were found to be competent along the following; (1) establishing certain basic problems and issues in school and community; (2) responsible for meeting the needs of the community and changing its behavior in certain aspects; (3) securing community support for the school; (4) working cooperatively with other agencies in the community; (5) responsible in using the total resources of the school to the community; (6) defining clearly the purpose of the community; and (7) directing activities of out-of-school youth.

The Educator's Diary (2006) stated that a good, effective and a successful teacher thinks in terms of human dignity; controls his behavior; respect the physical needs of his pupils; is consistent, impartial, attentive, courteous, and enthusiastic. In addition, a good teacher should participate, comment favorably, smile and laugh, work hard, use a conversational manner; hold pupils to high standards; trust pupils; "always leave the door open and consult others." Robbins (2005) pointed out that a competent teacher has an opportunity and responsibility in many ways or situations to guide in the wide range of problems and decisions that confront them. These opportunities are from time to time within the regular classroom particularly during homeroom period, in study rooms and in student activity situations. He has two responsibilities which he must fulfill if he is to realize his maximum usefulness. The first responsibility is to make himself available and approachable to pupils so that they will feel free to come to him as a personal confidant, adult friend, and informal counselor-interested and concerned, but not curious about their lives and personal problems. If the school has an organized guidance program, the classroom has a second responsibility to refer pupils to appropriate specialist for the kind of special help they need whether personal, academic or vocational in nature.

Redl (2005) pointed out that the teachers' self-understanding is an important pre-requisite to his understanding of others. This understanding, in turn is necessary for becoming a truly effective teacher.

Bailey (2005) states that the major responsibility of a teacher as a classroom teacher is to lead and guide pupils. In the modern school this is considered a democratic and cooperative process, with respect to the dignity of each individual involved. He stresses that in guiding class groups, the teacher's chief work will involve helping them define their most pressing needs and interest and problems; helping them understand themselves better; and helping them understand their families, their friends, their whole community.

Halloway (2004) states that competent teachers never stop trying to improve themselves. They cannot do otherwise, because no matter how effective a teacher maybe, if he becomes complacent or self-satisfied, he is professionally dead or dying.

Mood (2016) underscored the qualities that make an effective teacher namely: Give attention to what the students are saying; Provide each student with a sense of personal worth; Develop each student's self-confidence and respect his ability to learn; Assume a posture of moral or intellectual superiority; Minimize conflict with students; Minimize lecturing; Provide an open and relax atmosphere; Generate activity among students; Be on guard against apathy and boredom. Show concern for the wellbeing of each student in the class; Try not to let students' fall-behind; Diversify teacher; Ask your students about your teaching; Teach the best you can; Interact with colleagues; Tone down grading systems; and Be a model.

Garrison, (2015) in his book *Psychology of Adolescent* underscored that teachers' effectiveness in values formation, for adolescent is accounted for by the following teacher's attributes: Clearly defined values; Consistently in these values; Respect for the value patterns that are best learned from the examples rather than from mottos and rules; Recognized that learning situations for value patterns are not easily effective for all learners; Understanding the operation of the learning process in the development of value patterns; and Understanding the adolescent as a dynamic product of the interrelation of heredity and environment. As Hurlock (2006) pointed out that in Basic Education, teachers are the most important single factor in the child's personality which suggests that the teacher-student relationship plays a vital role in the personality development of the students.

Quintos (2015) conducted a study of the effect on teachers' competence by professional growth activities in Bataan Polytechnic State College.

Findings showed that professional growth activities were significantly related to level of teaching competency.

Mallari (2015) conducted a study on the correlated of effective elementary schools.

Findings showed that supervision and interpersonal relationship are imperative for effective administration. The teachers' commitment, membership in professional organization, and teacher trainings and scholarships are significantly correlated with efficiency.

Other findings revealed that the size of school and number of teacher also cont. Emphasis on the basic skills is a very important factor that contributes to pupils' performance.

De Guzman (2015) made a study on the correlates on social values of Manila Public High School students. He used Gordon's Survey of Interpersonal Values (SIV) and a Pasao's Self-Concept Scale in gathering the pertinent data.

The researcher found out that the ranked values of students were as follows: (1) parental and family concerns, (2) conformity, (3) leadership, (4) benevolence, (5) social acceptance, (6) educational concerns, (7) economic security, (8) independence and (9) support and recognition.

Liberman (2005) conducted a study entitled, "The Power of the Teacher". This study was based on the assumption that if the teacher is the most significant leader in the school, then it would be reasonable to assume that his influence would be evident among those whom he leads. The findings revealed that when the teachers share decision-making with his student, when he involves the student in organizing the classroom deal with its problems, the student responded with higher morale and greater performance. Under such leadership, teachers become more willing to engage in the process of bringing about fruitful change in the school. She further found out that when pupils were given little decision-making power, they themselves were reluctant to give decision-making power to their schoolmate.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the theory of Behavioral Modification by Ornstein (2004). This theory primarily involves techniques and methods though giving of praises and rewards to elaborate reinforcement training. This is applied in this study to strengthen teaching competencies thereby increasing their social involvement.

The study is also premised on the theory of social learning or observation learning which postulated learning through observing the behavior of another person, called a model (Feldman, 1997). According to Bandura (1986), observational learning takes four steps: (1) paying attention and perceiving the most critical features of another person's behavior, (2) remembering the behavior (3) reproducing the action, (4) being motivated to learn and carry-out the behavior. Not all behavior witnessed is learned or carried-out. Instead of learning occurring through trial and error, with successes being reinforced and failures punished, many important skills are learned through observation processes. It is on this context that teacher should be aware of the characteristics of students at the same time should possess high level of professional and personal qualities in order that they can be more effective in carrying out their tasks relative to their commitment.

It is also premised on the theory on Symbolic Interactionism. According to Reynolds (2004), this is anchored on the major premises, namely; (a) individuals act toward things and people on the basis of the meanings that things have for them; (b) the meaning of such things are

derived from, or arise out of the social interaction that individuals have with one another, and (c) these meanings are handled in, modified through, an interpretive process used by individual to deal with the things and other people they encounter. The symbolic interactionism perspective views the individual as a social product who is influenced by others but also maintains distance from other and is able to initiate individual action. Thus, this theory can contribute to increase teachers' teaching competencies along personal qualities by way of establishing interpersonal relationship with people around them particularly to co-faculty members, students, top management or administrators and the community as a whole.

Conceptual Framework

Quality education is the primordial goal of basic education. In attaining its goal, teaching-learning process should be strengthened thru teacher's professional and personal qualities.

The schematic presentation of the study is illustrated in input-process-output model. The input consisted of the profile of the teacher respondents such as age, sex, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities along communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability, and patience, and the problem met by teachers.

The process consisted of an analysis of the profile, extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities and the problems met by teachers. It also consisted the formulation of proposed plan of action.

Finally, the output is the of proposed action plan to improve the professional and personal qualities of teachers.

The figure below shows the paradigm of the study.

Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities in the Public High Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2024-2025.

Strengthening the professional and personal qualities of the faculty in the High Schools of Calasiao is important and timely. The professional appearance and attitude of a faculty will have an impact on the academic progress of the students.

This prompted the researcher to conduct the survey on professional and personal qualities of the faculty members of Public High Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I.

Specifically, it will sought answers to the following sub-questions:

1. What is the profile of the faculty members of Public Secondary Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao along the following variables?
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Highest Educational Attainment
 - d. Years of Teaching Experience and
 - e. Seminars/Trainings Attended for the last three (3) years?
2. To what extents do faculty members manifest professional qualities and practice personal attributes as perceived by themselves and their school administrators along:
 - a. Communication,
 - b. Listening,
 - c. Collaboration,
 - d. Adaptability, and
 - e. Patience.
3. Are there significant differences on the extent of teachers' professional manifestation and personal practices across their profile variables?
4. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which faculty members manifest professional qualities?
5. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities?
6. What are the strengths and weaknesses of teachers in their manifestation of professional and practice of personal qualities?
7. What action plan can be proposed to enhance the manifestation of the professional and personal qualities of the teachers?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference on the extent of teachers' manifestation and practices across their profile variables.
2. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers themselves and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities.
3. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers themselves and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study was conducted in the Public High Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2024-2025. There were 326 faculty members and 9 school Heads taken in complete enumeration. The variables that were investigated focused on determining profile variables of teachers, extents to which manifest professional and practice personal qualities such as communication, listening, collaboration, adaptability and patience.

Significance of the Study

The results of the study shall benefit the Curriculum Planners, School Administrators, Guidance Counselors, Teachers, Students, Parents, and the Researcher.

Curriculum Planners. They will profit from this study in terms of better way of planning the curriculum by giving more emphasis on professional and personal qualities of teachers to make it responsive to teaching-learning environment.

School Administrators. The results of the study may serve as an eye-opener for the consideration of the emphasis on school learning at the same time it will serve as inputs to the planning and implementation of appropriate curriculum enrichment including staff development relative to establishing a well-sounder and healthy comprehensive teaching competencies of teachers relative to professional ethics and their qualities.

Guidance Counselors. The results of the study shall benefit the guidance counselors from obtaining the necessary data and information on the status of teachers pertaining to their extent of practices of teaching competencies along the two (2) identified areas. Ultimately, these data can be used for strengthening the guidance program of the school.

Teachers. The study will give them their chance to improve their capability in promoting their professional and personal qualities.

Students. The study will help improve their academic performance out of their teachers' extent of practices relative to the identified teaching competencies.

Parents. The result of the study will make them realize that children in schooling but more importantly to provide children the necessary skills and knowledge along their role in education of their children is not just the provision of needs of their other traits and qualities to improve their total person.

Definition of Terms / Phrases

In order to present a more thorough and comprehensive insights in this study, the following terms and phrases will be defined either lexically and/or operationally:

Age. In this study, it refers to the age bracket of public secondary school teachers which are classified as 21-39 years, 40-55 years and 56 and Above.

Adaptability. In this study it refers to the ability of the teachers to give highest respect to students and feel welcome anytime and apply the principle of individual differences to help students cope up to any challenges.

Communication. In this study it refers to the ability of the teachers to relay to their students the activities in school projects, assignment, guide them to be successful by setting a good and high standard to believe in themselves as they provide clear requirements for the class.

Collaboration. In this study, it refers to the ability of the teachers to the agreeable in most school activities, projects, and extra-curricular activities in and out of the school with strategies to help students and positively with one another in performing a certain task.

Highest Educational Attainment. In this study, it refers to the degree obtained by teachers which are classified as Bachelor's Degree, Master of Arts (M.A.) Degree and Doctorate Degree.

Listening. In this study, it refers to the attitude of the teachers to make the students feel they are welcome and available anytime they are needed, sharing personal experience and interest in students and connect with them personally.

Length of Service. In this study, it refers to the teaching experience of teachers in the public secondary schools which are categorized as 0-10 Years and 11 Years and Above.

Personal Qualities. They refer to the teacher's personality which includes his philosophy, interests, attitudes, beliefs, emotional maturity and his interrelations with his students and colleagues in the manner he responds to various situations and how these people respond to his behavior (Zulueta, 2006).

Professional Qualities. They refer to qualities which undoubtedly influence teaching-learning process and highly attributive to teaching competence relative to mastery of the subject matter, medium of instruction, methodology of teaching, art of questioning, classroom management and evaluation skills (Zulueta, 2006).

Chapter 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research methodology of the study. It includes its research design, the locale and population of the study, the instrument to be used, data gathering procedure and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The descriptive design was used in this study. This research method was used to establish the prevailing status or conditions in a particular area of concern. It is also suitable to situations which call for the analysis of differences without variable manipulation. Hence, the descriptive method is appropriate for the study.

The present study focused on determining the profile of respondent teachers and their extents to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities. It also sought to determine the significance of the differences between the perceptions faculty member and their school administrators on the extents to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities at 5% level of significance.

Locale and Population of the Study

The study was conducted in the Public Secondary Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2024-2025. The subjects of the study consisted of the total enumeration of all the faculty members of the High Schools in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I and the school administrators.

Table 1

List of Teachers and School Administrators in the Municipality of Calasiao

Schools	Teachers	School Administrators
1. Calasiao Comprehensive National High School	190	10
2. Bued National High School	49	3

3. Doyong-Malabago National High School	47	5
4. Buenlag National High School	19	3
Total	305	21

Data-Gathering Procedure

The researcher first sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Pangasinan I pertaining to the conduct of the study. Likewise, she also sought permission from the school administrators from the public secondary schools covered in the study. After the approval to conduct the study the set of questionnaire was personally administered by the researcher to all the faculty members in the said schools. It took her three (3) weeks for both floating and collecting the said questionnaires. After the retrieval the researcher tallied the results for analysis and interpretation of the data.

Data-Gathering Instrument

The research study used the questionnaire as the data gathering instruments. It consisted of two (2) parts.

Part I consisted of the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience and seminars / trainings attended for the last three (3) years.

Part II consisted of the indicators on professional and personal qualities of teachers. This was adopted from Zulueta (2006) in his book *Principles and Methods of Teaching*, and the study of Rodelio I. Macaranas "Professional and Personal Qualities of Public Secondary School Teachers in Malasiqui, Pangasinan (2015).

Statistical Treatment of Data

Problem number 1 on determining the profile of teachers was answered by using frequency counts and percentages. Problem number 2 on determining the extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities was answered by using 4-Value Likert Scale with the average weighted mean (AWM) and their descriptive ratings as follows:

Scale	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Rating	
	(3.36-4.00)	Always (A)	
4	(2.51-3.35)	Often (O)	- 5 times a week
3	(1.76-2.50)	Sometimes (S)	- 4 times a week
2	(1.00-1.75)	Rarely (R)	- 2-3 times a week
1			- Once a week

Problem number 3 on determining the significant difference on the extent of teachers manifest professional and personal qualities across their profile variables was answered by using the t-test for sex, years of teaching experience and seminars/trainings attended for the last three years. However, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used under profile variables age and highest educational attainment and then subjected to Post-hoc test particularly the Scheffe's test or S-test to purposely determine the significance of the differences between pair of means one after the other.

Formula:

$$t = \frac{X_1 - X_2}{SD_x}$$

Where:

X_1 = First mean

X_2 = Second mean

SD_x = Standard error of difference between the two means

$$F = \frac{\text{Mean-Square for Between Groups}}{\text{Mean-Square for Within Groups}}$$

Post-hoc test using the Scheffe's test

$$F = \frac{(xX^1 - X^2)}{\text{Mean-Square for Within Groups}}$$

Post-hoc test using the Scheffe's test

$$F = \frac{(X^1 - X^2)^2}{S^2 W (N_1 + N_2) \div N_1 N_2}$$

Problem number 4 on the significant differences between the perceptions of the faculty members / teachers themselves and their school administrators on their extent of manifestation along professional qualities was answered by using the t-test.

Problem number 5 on the significant differences between faulty members the perceptions of the faculty members / teachers themselves and their school administrators on their extent of practices along personal qualities was answered by using the t-test.

Problem number 6 the strengths and weaknesses of the teachers in the extent of their professional and personal qualities of manifestations and practices were answered by using the average weighted mean of 251 and above strengths and 3.35 below were considered their weaknesses. Problem number 7 on formulation of proposed action plan was based on the findings of the study.

Scale	Statistical Limit	Descriptive Rating
4	(3.36-4.00)	Serious (S)
3	(2.51-3.35)	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	(1.76-2.50)	Fairly Serious (FS)
1	(1.00-1.75)	Least Serious (LS)

Chapter 3

Results and Discussion

Gender

Table 2 presents the profile of the teacher respondents along Sex

Table 2
Profile of the Teacher Respondents Along Sex
(N=32)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	74	22.70%
Female	252	77.30%
Total	305	100%

Table 3 reveals that 74 or 22.70% of the teachers are males. On the other hand, 252 or equivalent to 77.30% are females. The data reveal that the females outnumbered the males.

This is caused by a situation that most of the males prefer to take up non-education courses like architecture, engineering, commerce and others over education course.

Highest Educational Attainment

Data on highest educational attainment of teachers are presented on table 4.

Table 3
Profile of the Teacher Respondents Along
Highest Educational Attainment
(N=326)

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
BS Graduate	74	22.70%
M.A. Graduate	68	20.86%
Doctorate Graduate	9	2.76%
Total	352	46.32%

It is evident in table 4 that 249 or 76.38% of the teachers are BS Graduates. However, only 68 or equivalent to 20.86% are graduates of Master of Arts while only 9 or 2.76% are graduates of Doctorate.

This indicates that only few teachers are full-fledged post graduate degrees. This may be caused by some factors financial constraint, social obligations, daily family financial maintenance, education of children and others. These priorities cannot be underestimated so as to maintain the respective obligations of teachers. This situation holds true in most of the schools in the division.

Brookfield (2004) pointed out that when teacher enter the profession. The acquisition of knowledge and skills is a continuing process and is enhanced by professional studies. If teachers hope to be effective and apply in their work they do not need to be prepared for each day's lesson but they also need to possess a variety of skills working with people, with students, colleagues, supervisor and parents.

Much more, they need to have a general education and knowledge of the subject they teach.

Years of Teaching Experience

Table 4 presents the profile of the teacher respondents along Years of Teaching Experience.

Table 4
Profile of the Teacher Respondents Along
Years of Teaching Experience
(N=326)

Years of Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
0-10 Years	184	56.44%
11 Years and Above	142	43.56%
Total	326	100%

Table 4 reveals that 184 or 56.44% of 326 teacher respondents have teaching experiences from 0-10 years. However, 142 or 43.56% gave teaching experiences from 11 years and up.

This simply implies that majority of the teacher respondents are still young in the service. The length of service has great deal of importance to the growth and status of teachers and gives efforts on her teaching manifestations within the context of professional qualities.

As Macomber (2004) pointed out with each years of experience a teachers' professional competence in teaching increases.

Seminars/Trainings Attended for the Last Three (3) Years

Data on Seminars/Trainings Attended of Teachers are presented in Table 5.

Table 5
Profile of the Teacher Respondents Along Seminars/Trainings Attended for the Last Three
(3) Years
(N=326)

Seminars/Trainings Attended for the Last Three (3) Years	Frequency	Percentage
1-5	216	66.26%
6 and Above	110	33.74%
Total	326	100%

Table 5 reveals that greater number of teacher respondents have 1-5 attendance in seminars/trainings as shown in the data in which there are 216 or equivalent to 66.26% out of 326 teacher respondents. However, there are 110 or 33.74% of the teacher respondents who have acquired 6 or more instances of attendance and participants.

This is caused by several factors. One is the policy of the DepEd that teacher should minimize interruption of classes so as to ensure not only quality but quantity of learning. Other maybe attributed to the financial constrain of teachers in the event that they are the ones shouldering the seminars registration fees.

Mallari (2020) in her study revealed that teachers from trainings and scholarship are significantly correlated with the efficiency of teachers asides from intensive supervision and exemplary interpersonal relationship.

Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional and Practice Personal Qualities as Perceived by Themselves and their School Administrators.

Table 6 presents the extent to which teachers manifest Professional Qualities.

Table 6
Extent to Which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities

A. Professional Qualities	Teachers (N=326)		School Administrators (N=19)		Overall	
	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.16	Often	3.20	Often	3.22	Often
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.10	Often	3.09	Often	3.10	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.05	Often	3.02	Often	3.04	Often
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.42	Sometimes	2.40	Sometimes	2.41	Sometimes
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.76	Often	2.72	Often	2.74	Often
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.	2.45	Sometimes	2.43	Sometimes	2.44	Sometimes
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.28	Always	3.30	Always	3.29	Always
8. Awareness on the art	3.11	Often	3.08	Often	3.10	Often

of questioning.							
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.40	Sometimes	2.42	Sometimes	2.41	Sometimes	
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.20	Often	3.18	Often	3.19	Often	
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.90	Often	2.88	Often	2.89	Often	

Table 6 shows ten (10) indicators on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities. Data revealed that the school administrators rated the teachers ranging from 2.42 to 3.30. The top five (5) indicators are namely; Conduct summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught (3.30), Mastery of subject matter (3.20), Awareness on classroom management including discipline (3.18), Mastery of medium of instruction (3.09) and Awareness of the art of questioning (3.08).

However, the lowest three (3) indicators rated by school administrators are activities relative to instructional materials and facilities, Employing appropriate methods, strategies and techniques, attendance and participants in seminars workshops. The overall average weighted mean is 2.89 described as “Often”.

The teacher on the other hand, rated themselves as “Often” in six (6) indicators. These are: Mastery of the subject matter (3.16), Mastery of the medium of instruction (3.10), Updates and upgrades the assigned subject thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc (3.05), Awareness on the level of intellectual and emotional maturity of children (2.76), Awareness on the art of questioning (3.11) and Awareness on classroom including discipline (3.20). In general the teachers rated themselves as “Often”.

Further analysis of the data shows that the overall extent of teachers’ manifestations along professional qualities is described as “Often” as evidenced by their average weighted mean of 2.89. This implies that the teachers are aware of some indicators along professional qualities like Awareness on classroom management including discipline, mastery of subject matter, Awareness on the art questioning including regular conduct of summative evaluation. The significance of the study can not be disregarded. It can basically contribute to improve the teaching-learning process.

It is saddening to note, however, that there are some indicators as revealed by a descriptive rating of “Sometimes” namely General understanding of other branches/field of knowledge, Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children and Employs Appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.

Abuera (2004) noted that the need for an adequate knowledge and orientation on the different teaching strategies and techniques for instructional competencies and other related areas on the part of the school administrators and teachers cannot be underestimated. They are the basic resources for the teachers in the achievement of maximum educational outcomes. On

this score, it is important for the secondary teachers and school administrators to acquire and develop instructional competencies and other related areas that will provide them direction and stimulate them to work out innovations in the school process.

Data on the Extent to Which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities and Perceived in Table 7.

Table 7 presents data on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities.

Table 7
Extent to Which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities

B. Personal Qualities Indicators	Teachers (N=326)		School Administrators		Overall	
	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.18	Often	3.20	Often	3.19	Often
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.14	Often	3.12	Often	3.13	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.05	Often	3.11	Often	3.08	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.19	Often	3.15	Often	3.17	Often
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.12	Often	3.08	Often	3.10	Often
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.10	Often	3.04	Often	3.07	Often
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.35	Always	3.31	Always	3.33	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.34	Sometimes	2.30	Sometimes	2.33	Sometimes
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.38	Always	3.36	Always	3.37	Always
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.41	Always	3.42	Always	3.42	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization	2.46	Sometimes	2.48	Sometimes	2.47	Sometimes

activities.						
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.44	Sometimes	2.46	Sometimes	2.45	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	2.43	Sometimes	2.41	Sometimes	2.42	Sometimes
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.70	Always	3.68	Always	3.69	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.66	Always	3.62	Always	3.64	Always
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.06	Often	3.05	Always	3.06	Often

Data in table 7 reveal that the school administrators rated their teachers as “Always” to indicators 7, 9, 10, 14 and 15. These are namely: Observes proper grooming and attire at all times (3.31), Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performance (3.36), Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time (3.42), Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching (3.68) and Shows respect for the dignity of the individual (3.62). On the other hand, they rated teachers as “Often”. These are: Shows refinement of manners (3.20), Commands attention and respect (3.12), Possesses well-modulated voice (3.11), Always appears presentable and pleasant (3.15), Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities (3.05) and Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability (3.04). The rest of the indicators are rated as “Sometimes” as evidence by their average weighted means. These are: Has a good sense of humor (2.32), Participates activity in cultural (2.48), Accepts and performs leadership roles completely in the school and in the community (2.46) and Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community (2.41).

The teachers, on the other hand, rated themselves as “Often” to indicators 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6. However, they rated themselves as “Always” to indicators 7, 9, 10 and 14. The rest of the indicators are described as “Sometimes”. These are namely; Has a good sense of humor (2.34), Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities (2.46), Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community (2.44), and Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.

Based on the overall perceptions, the teachers have performed well to activities concerning proper grooming, creativity and resourcefulness submission of reports on time and the subject of enthusiasm. However, activities where the teachers should have to focus more attention are: good sense of humor, participation in cultural and other related activities, competence and interpersonal relationship.

The combined perceptions of teachers and school administrators themselves show ratings

which are described as “Always”. These are indicators 7, 9, 10, 14 and 15 while indicators 8, 11, 12 and 13 are described as “Sometimes”. The rest of the indicators are described as “Often”.

Further analysis of the data reveals that the overall average weighted mean is 3.06 which is described as “Often”. This basically implies that teachers have not reach the desired extent of practices on personal qualities.

Aquino (2005) pointed out that an excellent teacher is a person who has the personal qualities of agreeableness, consideration for others, sincerity and the like, is professionally interested and competent; manifest scholarship and culture; respect children and is respected by children; and establishes wholesome pupil-teacher relationship.

Differences on the Extent to Which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities Across Their Profile Variables Age

Data on the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities with respect to Age are presented in table 8

Table 8 presents the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities with respect to Age

Table 8

Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities with Respect of Age

A. Professional Qualities	Profile Variables on Age					
	21-39 Years		40-55 Years		56-65 Years	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.25	Often	3.26	Always	3.28	Always
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.06	Often	3.08	Often	3.10	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.07	Often	3.10	Often	3.12	Often
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.38	Sometime s	2.42	Sometime s	2.42	Sometime s
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.81	Often	2.82	Often	2.45	Often
6. Employs appropriate	2.45	Sometime	2.46	Sometime	2.45	Sometime

methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.		s		s		s
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.28	Always	3.30	Always	3.29	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.15	Often	3.16	Often	3.16	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.42	Sometimes	2.40	Sometimes	2.42	Sometimes
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.20	Often	3.22	Often	3.23	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.90	Often	2.92	Often	2.91	Often

Computed F-value: 2.66

Critical value : 3.35 Alpha = 5%

Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation : There is no significant difference

Data in table 8 shows the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities across profile variable age which has consisted of three (3) categories namely: 21-39 years, 40-55 years and 56-65 years. The overall average weighted means of the 3 categories are 2.90, 2.92 and 2.91 respectively. These are described as "Often".

On the other hand, the computed F-value and the critical value at the .05 level of significance likewise shown in the table. As shown the computed F-value is 2.66 and the critical value is 3.35. Since the critical value is greater than the computed F-value, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there are no significant differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities.

It can therefore be inferred that age did not affect or influence the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities. This means that the teachers whether they are young or old are on the same level of manifestation.

Sex

Data on the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities with respect to Sex are presented in table 9.

Table 9 presents the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities across Sex.

Table 9
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities with Respect to Sex
(N=326)

A. Professional Qualities	Profile Variable Sex			
	Male		Female	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.26	Always	3.22	Often
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.08	Often	3.12	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.06	Often	3.04	Often
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.40	Sometimes	2.44	Sometimes
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.80	Often	2.72	Often
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.	2.44	Sometimes	2.46	Sometimes
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.29	Often	3.30	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.14	Often	3.09	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.41	Sometimes	2.39	Sometimes
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.22	Often	3.18	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.91	Often	2.90	Often

Computed t-value : 0.332

Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%

Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation : There is no significant difference

The teachers were grouped according to sex; male and female. The overall average weighted mean under male is 2.91 which is described as “Often”. The group under female is also described as “Often” as evidenced by the average weighted mean of 2.90.

Further scrutiny of the data shows that the computed t-value is 0.332 and the critical value is 2.048 using the .05 level of significance. This implies that there is no significant difference on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities in terms of sex. This means that the variable sex did not have an effect or influence in their extent of manifestation of professional qualities.

Highest Educational Attainment

Table 10 presents the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities across highest educational attainment.

Table 10
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities According to
Highest Educational Attainment
(N=326)

A. Professional Qualities	Highest Educational Attainment					
	BS Graduate (A)		M.A. Graduate (B)		Doctorate Graduate (C)	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.14	Often	3.20	Always	3.38	Always
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.08	Often	3.10	Often	3.13	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	2.98	Often	2.99	Often	3.11	Often
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.20	Sometim es	2.26	Sometim es	2.80	Sometim es
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.32	Sometim es	2.45	Sometim es	3.51	Always
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.	2.30	Sometim es	2.39	Sometim es	2.66	Sometim es
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.12	Often	3.26	Always	3.46	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.04	Often	3.08	Always	3.21	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.33	Sometim es	2.36	Sometim es	3.82	Sometim es
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.12	Often	3.19	Often	3.29	Always
Overall Average Weighted	2.76	Often	2.83	Often	3.24	Often

Mean					
Computed F-value:	89.93				
Critical value	: 3.35	Alpha =	5%		
Decision	:	Reject the Null Hypothesis			
Interpretation	:	There is no significant difference			
Comparing pairs of categories using Post Hoc test					
A VS B	:	2.33, Accept the Null Hypothesis			
A VS C	:	16.0, Reject the Null Hypothesis			
B VS C	:	13.67, Reject the Null Hypothesis			

Data in table 10 reveal the extent to which teachers practice professional qualities with respect to Highest Educational Attainment. These are grouped into three (3) namely: BS Graduate, M.A. Graduate and Doctoral Graduate.

It is evident in the same table that the computed F-value is 89.93 and a critical value is 3.35 at 5% level. Further analysis of the data reveals that the computed F-value is greater than the critical value so the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities with respect to Highest Educational Attainment.

It may be inferred that the highest educational attainment can give an effect on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities.

Years of Teaching Experience

Table 11 presents the differences on the extent to which teacher practice professional qualities across years of teaching experience.

Table 11
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities Across Years of Teaching Experience
 (N=326)

A. Professional Qualities	Years of Teaching Experience			
	0-10 Years		11 Years and Above	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.22	Often	3.26	Always
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.07	Often	3.13	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.06	Often	3.04	Often
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.40	Sometimes	2.44	Sometimes
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.74	Often	2.78	Often
6. Employs appropriate methods,	2.43	Sometimes	2.47	Sometimes

techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.		s		
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.26	Always	3.30	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.09	Often	3.13	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.41	Sometime s	2.38	Sometimes
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.16	Often	3.24	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.88	Often	2.92	Often

Computed t-value : 0.138

Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%

Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation : There is no significant difference

It is apparent in table 11 that the overall average weighted mean of teachers under 0-10 Years of teaching experience is 2.88 while under 11 years and above is 2.92. Both are described as "Often".

Further analysis of the data shows that the computed t-value is 0.138 and the critical value is 2.048. This means that, the null hypothesis of no significant difference at the .05 level of accepted. It can therefore be deduced that the length of service of teachers did not influence the extent to which they manifest professional qualities.

In other words, the year of teaching experience is not a factor to improve the extent of teachers' manifestations along professional qualities.

Seminars/Training Attended for the Last Three (3) Years

Table 12 presents the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities across seminars/trainings attended.

Table 12
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities According to Seminars / Trainings Attended for the Last 3 Years
(N=326)

A. Professional Qualities	Seminars/Trainings Attended for the Last Three Years			
	1-5		6 and Above	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.20	Often	3.28	Always
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.08	Often	3.12	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending	3.05	Often	3.07	Often

seminars, trainings, reading, etc.				
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.41	Sometimes	2.39	Sometimes
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.72	Often	2.76	Often
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.	2.44	Sometimes	2.42	Sometimes
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.28	Always	3.32	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.11	Often	3.12	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.42	Sometimes	2.38	Sometimes
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.14	Often	3.18	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.89	Often	2.90	Often

Computed t-value : 0.138
Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%
Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis
Interpretation : There is no significant difference

In other words, the year of teaching experience is not a factor to improve the extent of teacher's manifestation along professional qualities.

Seminars/Trainings Attended for the Last Three (3) Years

Table 13 presents the differences on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities across seminars/trainings attended.

Table 13
Differences Between Perception of Teachers and their School Administrators on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities

A. Professional Qualities	Teachers (N=326)		School Administrators (N=19)	
	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.24	Often	3.20	Always
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.10	Often	3.09	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.05	Often	3.02	Often

4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.42	Sometimes	2.40	Always
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.76	Often	2.72	Often
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.	2.45	Sometimes	2.43	Sometimes
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.28	Always	3.30	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.11	Often	3.08	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.40	Sometimes	2.42	Sometimes
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.20	Often	3.18	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.90	Often	2.88	Often

Computed t-value : 0.187
Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%
Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis
Interpretation : There is no significant difference

It is evident in the table that the computed t-value is 0.138 which is much lesser than the critical value of 2.048. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted considering that the computed t-value is smaller than the critical value. This implies that seminars/trainings attendance did not affect or influence the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities.

Differences Between the Perceptions of Teachers and Their School Administrators on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities and Practice Personal Qualities.

Data on the differences between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities are presented in table 14.

Table 14
Differences Between the Perceptions of Teachers and their School Administrators on the Extent to which Teachers Manifest Professional Qualities

A. Professional Qualities	Teachers (N=326)		School Administrators (N=19)	
	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.2	Often	3.2	Always

	4		0	
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.1 0	Often	3.0 9	Often
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.0 5	Often	3.0 2	Often
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.	2.4 2	Sometim es	2.4 0	Always
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.7 6	Often	2.7 2	Often
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.	2.4 5	Sometim es	2.4 3	Sometim es
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.2 8	Always	3.3 0	Always
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.1 1	Often	3.0 8	Often
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.	2.4 0	Sometim es	2.4 2	Sometim es
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.2 0	Often	3.1 8	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.9 0	Often	2.8 8	Often

Computed t-value : 0.192

Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%

Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation : There is no significant difference

Data in table 14 reveals that the overall average weighted mean of the perception of teachers is 2.90 which is described as “Often” while the overall average weighted mean of the perception of school administrators is 2.88 also described as “Often”. It is apparent that the difference between their two (2) means is only .02.

It is on the same table that the computed t-value is 0.192 while the critical value is 2.048 at the 5% level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted in the event that the computed value is smaller than the critical value.

This means that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers manifest professional qualities. This implies that the two (2) perceptions are on the same level or they do not vary.

Table 14 presents the differences between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities

Table 15
Differences Between Perception of Teachers and their School Administrators on the Extent to which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities (N=345)

B. Personal Qualities	Teachers (N=326)		School Administrators (N=19)	
	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.18	Often	3.20	Often
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.14	Often	3.12	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.05	Often	3.11	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.19	Often	3.15	Often
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.12	Often	3.08	Often
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.10	Often	3.04	Often
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.35	Always	3.31	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.34	Sometimes	2.32	Sometimes
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.38	Always	3.36	Always
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.41	Always	3.42	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.	2.46	Sometimes	2.48	Sometimes
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.44	Sometimes	2.46	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	2.43	Sometimes	2.41	Sometimes
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.70	Always	3.68	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.66	Always	3.62	Always
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.06	Often	3.05	Often

Computed t-value : 0.048
 Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%
 Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation : There is no significant difference

It is evident in table 15 that the overall average weighted means of teachers and their school administrators are 3.06 and 3.05 respectively. Both are described as “Often”

Same table also shows that the computed t-value is .048 while the critical value is 2.048. This means that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators at the .05 level of significance in the event that the computed t-value is smaller than the critical value.

The basically implies that the perceptions of the two groups of respondents are of the same level.

Differences on the Extent to Which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities Across their Profile Variables

Age

Data on the differences on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities with respect to Age are presented in table 16.

Data in table 16 reveals that the overall average weighted mean of teachers under age bracket 21-39 years is 3.08 while mean of teachers under 40-55 years is 3.10 and teachers under age bracket 56-65 years is 3.11. All are described as “Often”.

Table 16

Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities with Respect to Age

B. Personal Qualities	Profile Variable on Age					
	21-39 Years		40-55 Years		56-65 Years	
Indicators	AWM	DE	AWM	DE	AWM	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.17	Often	3.19	Often	3.20	Often
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.12	Often	3.14	Often	3.15	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.07	Often	3.06	Often	3.07	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.19	Often	3.20	Often	3.21	Often
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.11	Often	3.10	Often	3.13	Often
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.09	Often	3.11	Often	3.12	Often

7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.32	Always	3.38	Always	3.34	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.30	Sometimes	2.35	Always	2.36	Sometimes
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.36	Always	3.38	Always	3.39	Always
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.40	Always	3.39	Always	3.41	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.	2.44	Sometimes	2.45	Sometimes	2.47	Sometimes
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.42	Sometimes	2.46	Sometimes	2.47	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	3.69	Always	3.71	Always	3.72	Always
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.64	Always	3.66	Always	3.69	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	2.89	Often	2.90	Often	2.91	Often
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.08	Often	3.10	Often	3.11	Often

Computed F-value: .084
 Critical value : 3.22 Alpha = 5%
 Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis
 Interpretation : There is no significant difference

A closer scrutiny of the data also shows that the computed t-value is .084 and the critical value is 3.22. This goes to show that the null hypothesis is accepted meaning, there is no significance difference in the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities in terms of Age.

This implies that profile variable age did not give effect on the extent to which they practice personal qualities regardless of whether classified as young, middle or old adult.

Sex

Data on the differences on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities with respect to Sex are presented in table 17.

Table 17 presents the differences in the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities with respect to Sex.

Table 17
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities with Respect to Sex

B. Personal Qualities	Profile Variable on Gender			
	Male		Female	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.16	Often	3.20	Often
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.13	Often	3.15	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.06	Often	3.05	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.19	Often	3.20	Often
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.13	Often	3.11	Often
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.08	Often	3.12	Often
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.37	Always	3.33	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.40	Sometimes	2.28	Always
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.34	Always	3.41	Always
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.38	Always	3.42	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.	2.44	Sometimes	2.47	Sometimes
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.42	Sometimes	2.46	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	2.42	Always	2.44	Always
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.71	Always	3.72	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.64	Often	3.68	Always

Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.06	Often	3.07	Often
Computed F-value:	.060			
Critical value	: 2.048	Alpha = 5%		
Decision	: Accept the Null Hypothesis			
Interpretation	: There is no significant difference			

It is evident in table 17 that the computed t-value is .060 which much lesser than the critical value of 2.048. This means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

This means that there is no significant difference on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities with respect to sex. This basically implies that profile variable sex did not influence the extent of their practices along personal qualities.

Highest Educational Attainment

Table 18 present the differences on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities across highest educational attainment.

Data in table 18 reveal the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities with respect to Highest Educational Attainment. These are grouped into three (3) categories namely: BS Graduate, M.A. Graduate and Doctorate Graduate.

It is evident in the same table that the computed F-value is 26.39 while the critical value is 3.22. This means that the null hypothesis is rejected meaning as a whole, there is significant difference on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities across highest educational attainment. This implies that highest educational attainment can give effect or influence on their extent of their practice along personal qualities.

Table 18
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities According to Highest Educational Attainment
(N=326)

B. Personal Qualities	Highest Educational Attainment					
	BS Graduate (A)		M.A. Graduate (B)		Doctorate Graduate (C)	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.01	Often	3.12	Often	3.32	Always
2. Commands attention and respect.	2.98	Sometime s	3.01	Often	3.15	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	2.96	Sometime s	3.02	Often	3.12	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.07	Often	3.18	Often	3.32	Always

5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.04	Often	3.10	Often	3.21	Often
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.00	Often	3.13	Often	3.26	Always
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.16	Always	3.27	Always	3.42	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.11	Sometimes	2.33	Sometimes	2.58	Sometimes
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.18	Always	3.31	Always	3.47	Always
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.25	Always	3.42	Always	3.56	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.	2.24	Sometimes	2.44	Sometimes	2.68	Often
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.26	Sometimes	2.37	Sometimes	2.69	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	2.25	Sometimes	2.48	Sometimes	2.61	Often
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.60	Always	3.67	Always	3.82	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.51	Always	3.65	Always	3.78	Always
Overall Average Weighted Mean	2.91	Often	3.03	Often	3.20	Often

Computed F-value: 26.39

Critical value : 3.22 Alpha = 5%

Decision : Reject the Null Hypothesis

Interpretation : There is no significant difference

Comparing Pairs of Categories Using Post Hoc Test

A VS B	:	6.54, Reject the Null Hypothesis
A VS C	:	8.65, Reject the Null Hypothesis
B VS C	:	2.12, Accept the Null Hypothesis

Further, in order to compare the means of the two (2) categories one after the other, as to determine the differences, the Post-Hoc test was employed.

Same table reveals that pair of categories A VS B has a computed F-value of 6.54. This means that there lies significant difference, do the same with A VS C with computed F-value of 8.65. However, the last pair of categories which is B VS C shows that the null hypothesis is accepted as proven by its computed F-value of 2.12 which is short of the critical value of 3.22. This means that the respondent teachers under M.A. Graduate and Doctorate Graduate have similar perceptions.

Years of Teaching Experience

Table 19 presents the Differences on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities across years of teaching experience.

Table 19 reveals that the groups of teachers classified as 0-10 years of teaching experiences has obtained an overall average weighted mean of 3.05 which is described as "Often". The other group with 11 years and Above has obtained 3.08 which has also descriptive equivalent of "Often".

Table 19

Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities in Terms of Years of Teaching Experience (N=326)

B. Personal Qualities	Years of Teaching Experience			
	0-10 Years		11 Years and Above	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.19	Often	3.20	Often
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.12	Often	3.16	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.06	Often	3.05	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.18	Often	3.20	Often
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.10	Often	3.14	Often
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.09	Often	3.11	Often
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.34	Always	3.36	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.33	Sometimes	2.35	Sometimes
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.36	Always	3.40	Always

10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.40	Always	3.42	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.	2.45	Sometimes	2.47	Sometimes
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.40	Sometimes	2.48	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	2.41	Sometimes	2.45	Sometimes
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.68	Always	3.72	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.67	Always	3.64	Always
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.05	Often	3.08	Often

Computed t-value : 0.186
Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%
Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis
Interpretation : There is no significant difference

The data on the table show that the computed t-value is 0.186 and a critical value of 2.048. This means that there is no significant difference on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities across years of teaching experience at .05 level of significance. This implies that years of teaching experience did not affect or influence their extent of practices along personal qualities.

Seminars/Trainings Attended for the Last Three (3) Years

Table 20 presents the differences on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities across seminar/trainings attended.

Table 20
Differences on the Extent to which Teachers Practice Personal Qualities According to Seminars/Trainings for the Last Three (3) Years
(N=326)

B. Personal Qualities	Years of Teaching Experience			
	0-10 Years		11 Years and Above	
Indicators	AW M	DE	AW M	DE
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.16	Often	3.19	Often
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.13	Often	3.15	Often
3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.04	Often	3.06	Often
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.19	Often	3.19	Often
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school	3.10	Often	3.14	Often

activities.				
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.08	Often	3.12	Often
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.34	Always	3.36	Always
8. Has a good sense of humor.	2.32	Sometimes	2.36	Sometimes
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.36	Always	3.40	Always
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.40	Always	3.42	Always
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.	2.44	Sometimes	2.48	Sometimes
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.	2.45	Sometimes	2.43	Sometimes
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.	2.44	Sometimes	2.43	Sometimes
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.69	Always	3.72	Always
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.65	Always	3.67	Always
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.05	Often	3.11	Often

Computed F-value: 0.32
 Critical value : 2.048 Alpha = 5%
 Decision : Accept the Null Hypothesis
 Interpretation : There is no significant difference

It is evident in table 20 that the overall weighted mean of the group of teachers under 1-5 attendance in Seminars/Trainings Attended is 3.05. It is described "Often". On the other hand, the group with 6 and above attendance has an average weighted mean of 3.11 which is also described as "Often".

The data on the table also reveal a computed t-value of 0.32 against a critical value of 2.048. This means that there is no significant difference on the extent to which they practice personal qualities across seminars/trainings attended. It can therefore be deduced that seminars/trainings did not influence the extent of practice of teachers along personal qualities.

Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers on the Extent to Which They Manifest Professional and Practice Personal Qualities

The strengths and weaknesses of teachers based on the criteria adopted are shown in the tables that follow.

Strengths and Weaknesses Along Professional Qualities

Table 21 reveals the strengths and weaknesses of teachers along Professional Qualities.

Table 21
Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers
Along Professional Qualities

Personal Qualities	Strengths	Weaknesses
Indicators		
1. Mastery of the subject matter.	3.22	
2. Mastery of the medium of instruction.	3.10	
3. Updates and upgrades the assigned subject/learning area thru attending seminars, trainings, reading, etc.	3.04	
4. General understanding of other branches / field of knowledge.		2.41
5. Awareness on the levels of intellectual and emotional maturity of children.	2.74	
6. Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.		2.44
7. Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught.	3.29	
8. Awareness on the art of questioning.	3.10	
9. Prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities.		2.41
10. Awareness on classroom management including discipline.	3.19	

It is evident in table 21 that there are more strengths (7) than weaknesses (3) along the dimension of professional qualities. The greater strengths are: Conducts summative evaluation every time a unit or chapter has been taught (3.29), Mastery of the subject matter (3.22) and Mastery of the medium of instruction (3.10). The weaknesses on the other hand, lie on prepares, organizes and utilizes appropriate instructional materials/facilities (2.41), General understanding of other branches/field of knowledge (2.41) and Employs appropriate methods, techniques and strategies to a particular teaching situation.

Strengths and Weaknesses Along Personal Qualities

Table 22 reveals the strengths and weaknesses of teachers along Personal Qualities.

Table 22
Strengths and Weaknesses of Teachers
Along Personal Qualities

Professional Qualities	Strengths	Weaknesses
Indicators		
1. Shows refinement of manners.	3.19	
2. Commands attention and respect.	3.13	

3. Possesses well-modulated voice.	3.08	
4. Always appears presentable and pleasant.	3.17	
5. Shows honesty and integrity in all school activities.	3.10	
6. Shows evidence of mental and physical health and emotional stability.	3.07	
7. Observes proper grooming and attire at all times.	3.33	
8. Has a good sense of humor.		2.33
9. Shows creativity and resourcefulness in his performances.	3.37	
10. Prepares and submits neat and accurate reports on time.	3.42	
11. Participates actively in cultural, professional and other organization activities.		2.47
12. Accepts and performs leadership roles competently in the school and in the community.		2.45
13. Gets along with students, co-teachers, school officials, staff and in the community.		2.42
14. Enthusiastic and enjoys teaching.	3.69	
15. Shows respect for the dignity of the individual.	3.64	

It is apparent in table 22 that there are more strengths (11) than weaknesses (4) along the dimension personal qualities. The strengths are found in activities relative to preparation and submission of reports, creativity and resourcefulness, proper grooming, showing good manners, modulated voice, enthusiasm, showing respect to others and mental and physical health including emotional stability. The weaknesses on the other hand are found in activities relative to sense of humor, participations in cultural, professional and other organization activities, leadership and interpersonal relationship.

The Proposed Plan of Action

The proposed action plan is intended to improve the professional and personal qualities of teachers in terms of their profile variables, extent of their practices including strengths and weaknesses on their extent to which they manifest professional and practice personal qualities.

The proposed plan has the following components.

- 1.Areas of Concern
- 2.Objectives / Targets
- 3.Activities / Strategies
- 4.Personal / Agencies Involved
- 5.Time Frame
- 6.Budget Estimate

- 7.Success Indicators

This is presented in matrix form found in the pages that follow.

Proposed Action Plan to Improve Professional and Personal Qualities of Public Secondary School Teachers in the Municipality of Calasiao Division I of Pangasinan

Areas of Concern	Objectives / Targets	Activities / Strategies	Persons / Agencies Involved	Time Frame	Budget Estimate	Success Indicator
I. Profile of the Teachers						
1. Highest Educational Attainment	- Update the educational attainment of teachers	a. Encourage teachers to enroll in the Graduate Program b. Asking the DepEd to maximize granting of scholarship in the Post Graduate Studies M.A. / Ed.D / Ph.D.	Teachers Principal School Division Superintendent	Year Round	P15,000	85% of the teachers shall have updated their educational attainment through enrolling in the Graduate Program.
II. Extent of Teachers Practice						
A. Professional Qualities						
1. Proper Preparation and Utilization of Appropriate Instructional Materials / Facilities	- Prepare and utilize properly the appropriate instructional materials / facilities	a. Solicit Funds and file resolution to proper authorities in the provision of instructional materials and	Teachers Principal Schools Division Superintendent	Year Round	P10,000	85% of the teachers shall have prepared and utilized the appropriate instructional materials/facilities.

		<p>facilities.</p> <p>b. Attend seminar - workshop regarding proper preparation and utilization of appropriate instructional materials and facilities</p> <p>c. Attend lectures, meetings and LAC session</p> <p>d. Invite resource persons along that area</p>					
2.	Employing Appropriate methods, techniques and strategies in teaching.	- Employ different appropriate methods, techniques and strategies in teaching.	- Attend seminar-workshop on the different methods, techniques and strategies in teaching.	Teachers School Principal	Summer Inset	P4,500	85% of the teachers shall have attended in seminars / trainings on the different appropriate methods, techniques and strategies in teaching.
3.	Regular conduct of Summative Evaluation	- Conduct / Administer Summative Test regularly	- Attend seminar-workshop on proper construction of summative	Teacher School Principal	Semestral Break	P3,500	85%of the teachers shall have conducted regularly summative evaluation to

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e test items - Attend lecture and orientation on the efficacies of conducting summative test - Read books and other supplementary materials relative to the proper preparation and conduct of summative test. 				pupils.
4. Mastery of Subject Matter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equip teachers on the mastery of subject matter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide additional and updated textbooks and other references from the DepEd thru channel - Attend seminar – workshop pertaining to mastery of subject 	Teacher School Principal	Year Round Summer Inset	P10,000	85% of the teachers shall have equipped themselves on the mastery of subject matter on the basis of identified strategies.

		matter through content – based methodology of teaching, proper utilization instructional materials and art of questioning				
5. Classroom management including discipline	- Equip teachers on the different approaches and their efficacies to classroom management including levels of effectiveness	- Attend division training on classroom - Attend lecture and LAC session focusing more on the efficacies and their level of effectiveness in classroom	Teachers School Principal	Semestral Break Year Round	P10,000	85% of the teachers shall have equipped themselves on the different approaches, efficacies of classroom management including their levels of effectiveness.
B. Personal Qualities						
1. Performing leadership roles in the school and in the community.	- Equip teachers on the “know-how” of leadership	- Attend training on leadership - Attend lecture and orientation on the efficacies	Teachers School Principal	Summer Inset Year round	P5,000	85% of the teachers shall have equipped themselves on the “know-how” of leadership.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - of leadership - Read books and other supplementary materials. 				
2. Good Sense of Humor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop teachers good sense of humor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attend lecture and orientation concerning good sense of humor - Read books and other supplementary materials on how to develop sense of humor. 	Teachers School Principal	Year round	P2,500	85% of the teachers shall have developed good sense of humor.
3. Interpersonal Relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acquire teachers on the “know-how” of establishing interpersonal relationship. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attend seminar-workshop on interpersonal relation - Read updated books and other supplementary materials related to establishing interpersonal 	Teachers School Principal	Summer Inset Year round	P5,000	85% of the teachers shall have acquired the “know-how” of interpersonal relationship.

		<p>nal relationship.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attend lecture and discussion on the efficacies of interpersonal relationship. 					
4.	<p>Participations in cultural, professional and other organizational activities</p>	<p>- Participate actively in cultural, professional and other organizational activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attend District LAC session and lecture on the efficacies of active participations to cultural, professional and other organizational activities - Reading updated books and other supplementary references - Viewing portrayal of cultural and other organizati 	Teacher School Principal	<p>Semestral Break</p> <p>Year round</p>	P10,000	85% of the teachers shall have actively participated in cultural, professional and other organizational activities.

		onal activities				
5. Showing evidence of mental, physical and emotional stability.	- Equip teachers with mental, physical and emotional stability	- Attend training on establishing mental and emotional stability - Attend lecture and orientation - Read books and other relative to mental, physical and emotional stability - Viewing relative to the acquisition of mental, physical and emotional stability	Teachers School Principal			85% of the teacher shall have equipped themselves with mental, physical and emotional stability.

Chapter 4

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the summary of significant findings, conclusions, generated from the findings and recommendations made based on the findings and conclusions.

Summary

The study sought to determine the extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities in the Municipality of Calasiao, Division of Pangasinan I during the school year 2015 – 2016 in terms of teachers' profile, extent to which teachers manifest professional and practice personal qualities including their strengths and weaknesses. The respondent of the study covered nineteen (19) public secondary schools with a total enumeration of 305 teachers and 19 school administrators.

Findings

The salient findings of the study are as follows:

1. Most of the teachers were females, within the age bracket from 21-39 years, BS graduates, have attended seminars/trainings with five (5) attendance or less for the past three (3) years and have been service for 10 years or less.
2. The extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities were described as "Often".
3. There were no significant differences on the extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities across profile variables age, gender, years of teaching experience and seminars/trainings attended except highest educational attainment.
4. There was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice professional qualities.
5. There was no significant difference between the perceptions of teachers and their school administrators on the extent to which teachers practice personal qualities.
6. There were strengths and weaknesses of teachers in the practice of professional and personal qualities. In some areas, there were more strengths than weaknesses.
7. A proposed action plan to improve the extent to which teachers practice professional and personal qualities was formulated.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. Most of the teachers were not fully equipped with the needed trainings and experiences in the different areas of professional and personal qualities.
2. Teachers had not reached the desired extent of teachers' practices especially along personal qualities.
3. Highest educational attainment has more effect than profile variables age, gender, years of teaching experience and seminars/training attended.
4. The perception of teachers on the extent to which they manifest professional qualities was reinforced by the perception of their school administrators. Hence, their perceptions do not vary.
5. The perceptions of teachers and their school administrators were of the same level.
6. The strengths of teachers dominate their weaknesses.

7. An action plan to improve the professional and personal qualities of teachers was formulated.

Recommendations

The following recommendations was hereby forwarded:

1. The proposed plan of action to improve then professional and personal qualities should be presented to the Schools Division Superintendent for adoption and implementation.
2. Teachers must be encouraged to attend sufficient number of seminar training and be given the opportunities to practice their professional and personal qualities.
3. Teachers and School heads must work together to cultivate their personal and professional qualities.

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